

Influence of playing online video games on Filipino college students' confidence in speaking English

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ABSTRACT

Online video games that require players to communicate in English provide opportunities for students to practice their language skills and overcome their fear of speaking in English. Unfortunately, the literature reveals an existing gap in investigating how such games can influence students' confidence in speaking English, especially in the Philippine context. Therefore, this study surveyed 148 Filipino college English-as-a-second language (ESL) students to examine differences in their perceived confidence in speaking English depending on learner variables such as gender, time spent online gaming (TSOG), number of games played (NOGP), self-rated speaking proficiency (SRSP), and game interactivity. Using independent t-tests and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) analyses, results revealed statistically significant differences in the development of communication skills in English (DCSE) depending on the TSOG, willingness to communicate (WTC) in English depending on the NOGP, and enhancement of communication skills in English, active participation in class, and reduced anxiety in using English (RAUE) depending on the SRSP. This exploratory study indicates that online video games can be valuable tools in increasing English speaking confidence among Filipino college students. Further research is posited to understand the extent to which online games influence ESL learners' speaking confidence in different educational and cultural contexts.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Video gaming has gained popularity across the world among different individuals of various age groups. Online gaming being the most popular type of gaming is distinguished by its mobility and game features [1]. In fact, in the Philippines alone, it has gained clamor among Filipino gamers aged 25 to 35 years old (38.92%), having the biggest share of gamers. Gen Z aged 18 to 24 constituted 13.2 million (30.05%) of the total 44.1 million (38.72%) gamers out of the entire Philippine population [2]. This considerable proportion of the population engaged in video games serves to illustrate the prevalence of online gaming. Such popularity may offer benefits to learners in enhancing their language skills.

Online video games, particularly for entertainment, can be beneficial in educational settings [3]. When used appropriately, game genres such as action role-playing games (action RPGs), massively multiplayer online role-playing games (MMORPGs), and strategy and tactical shooter games can contribute to overall cognitive and language development [4], [5]. For instance, Rodgers and Heidt [6] claimed that such games are prevalent extramural tools for language learning. Chen and Yang [7] asserted that such games can help college students improve their English listening, reading, vocabulary, and learning motivation. In addition, Chen and Yang [8] also reported that students thought the video games were beneficial to the improvement of their language skills in foreign language (FL) and their learning attitudes.

While video games present opportunities for language learners to develop specific language skills [9], there is a paucity of research that examines the influence of gender, time spent playing video games, number of games played (NOGP), speaking proficiency, and interactivity of video games on students' overall confidence in speaking English, particularly in the Philippine context. Given the popularity of mobile and computer video games among Gen Z and the benefits of online gaming, this study investigates the under-researched potentials of online video games in enhancing Filipino college students' confidence in speaking English. Hence, the findings of this study could inform language educators and curriculum developers on how to optimize online gaming as an effective supplementary tool for enhancing speaking confidence among English-as-a-second language (ESL) learners, potentially benefiting broader educational contexts.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Potential of online video games in developing language skills

Speaking confidently in English is one of the most essential and challenging skills to master for effective communication [10], [11]. Many language learners struggle to express themselves verbally in a foreign or second language due to a lack of confidence in speaking [12], [13]. Thus, several researches [14], [15] stressed the significance of addressing confidence issues in speaking English. In addition, other research [16], [17] recognized communicative activities such as role-playing and collaborative tasks to improve language skills, especially fluency, pronunciation, and intonation. However, such activities lack engagement in real communication and available resources for speaking in English classroom contexts [18], [19]. Therefore, researchers advocate the use of digital technologies such as video games as a supplementary tool for language instruction [20], [21].

Previous studies from different contexts examined the impact of video gaming on language learning [8], [9], [22]. Based on a survey conducted among 96 students aged 11-15 exploring the connection between video game playing and English proficiency, Rudis and Poštić [22] indicated that video games had a profound impact on language learning, particularly enhancing vocabulary and pronunciation, while also significantly increasing motivation among learners. Studies also found that commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) and online multiplayer video games reduced anxiety and increased confidence of ESL college students in using English [4], [23]. Such findings suggest that such types of video games can be a valuable tool for improving language skills, particularly by improving vocabulary, pronunciation, motivation, and confidence in speaking English [4], [22], [24], [25]. However, the related studies have focused on general language development rather than specifically addressing the relationship between online video games and speaking confidence.

2.2. Influence of learner variables and online video games on English speaking confidence

Previous studies have explored the impact of learner variables, such as gender, time spent gaming, speaking proficiency, and immersive online gaming experiences, on enhancing English speaking confidence. For instance, Borgonovi [26] examined gender differences in reading achievement linked to video gaming. Data from 145,953 students across 26 countries indicated that boys aged 15 years old generally scored lower in computer-based reading tests. Accordingly, single-player games benefit both genders, but frequent participation in collaborative online games is linked to lower achievement. Yuditseva [5] demonstrated that male players who preferred video games such as first-person shooters, MMORPGs, and adventure games exhibited greater vocabulary learning abilities compared to female players who preferred single-player simulation games. Soyooof and McLay [27] indicated that the COTS game, *Theft Auto: Chinatown Wars*, had a generally positive impact on the English language proficiency of 100 English language learners (aged 18-32) at a private language institute in Iran. While these studies suggest that such games can enhance language learning, there remains a gap in understanding how gender related to online video games affects the development of speaking confidence.

Previous studies have also suggested that time spent playing online video games could enhance language learning. Thorne and Reinhardt [28] reported that gamified language learning environments could increase learners' willingness to communicate (WTC). This, in turn, could positively influence speaking

confidence as learners feel more invested and interested in practicing their English-speaking skills. Study by Peterson [29] emphasized that online games provide informal speaking opportunities for learners. In fact, exposure to online video games provides students with the experience of practicing target language (TL) in an engaging way [30]. While playing games, learners can use English in a low-pressure and immersive environment. Thus, online games provide language learners with additional practice to improve their speaking confidence [31]. However, excessive time spent playing games can have negative effects on learners, such as reduced time for studying and completing academic tasks, decreased cognitive function due to sleep disturbances, decreased motivation for language learning, and social isolation [24], [26], [32].

Furthermore, relevant studies have shown a positive correlation between higher levels of speaking proficiency and increased confidence in speaking English [33]. As speaking proficiency improves, learners often feel more comfortable expressing themselves in English, leading to greater confidence in their speaking abilities [34]. In the Philippines, college learners who have greater proficiency in speaking English tend to exhibit higher levels of confidence when engaged in collaborative speaking tasks such as group activities or presentations [35]. While this finding is not explicitly connected between speaking proficiency and video games, it may reflect how video games as extracurricular activities can support language learning.

The interactivity of online video games can also contribute to the development of speaking confidence among language learners. For instance, Horowitz [4] reported that online multiplayer video games, such as World of Warcraft and Call of Duty, reduced communicative anxiety and increased WTC among college ESL students in Puerto Rico. Accordingly, such exposure is less likely to be received in the formal classroom context [4]. Furthermore, Kamali [36] discussed how task-based language learning (TBLL) in Second Life effectively changed 15 upper-intermediate Turkish students' negative perceptions of English and increased their motivation, confidence, and positive attitudes toward speaking English. These studies emphasize that the relaxed and interactive nature of the game can increase students' WTC and reduce their speaking anxiety, which can potentially increase their speaking confidence. Although related studies have reported the potential benefits of playing online video games in improving speaking confidence, there is still a gap in investigating such a relationship among Filipino students who still face confidence issues in speaking English. Therefore, this study aims to address this gap by answering the following questions:

- i) What are the perceived effects of online video games on Filipino college students' confidence in speaking English, depending on learner variables?
- ii) What relationships exist between learners' gaming preferences and their confidence in speaking English?

3. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1. Context and respondents

The respondents of the study involved university students from one of the state universities and colleges (SUC) in the Philippines. Students were enrolled in English related courses or in any subjects taught with English as the medium of instruction during the first semester in 2023. Specifically, the students were majoring in development communication, English literature, business administration and accountancy, veterinary science in medicine, engineering, environmental science, and tourism and management. As English serves as the medium of instruction in the Philippines, students from various year at University X could participate in the survey voluntarily.

3.2. Instrument and data collection

This study employed a two-part survey questionnaire. The first part gathered the profile of the respondents or the learners' variables such as gender, time spent online gaming (TSOG), NOGP, self-rated speaking proficiency (SRSP), and whether they played video games such as multiplayer or single video games, multiplayer online battle arena (MOBA), action RPG, MMORPG, strategy video games, and survival or tactical shooter games accordingly based on their respective websites. Such video games, mainly for entertainment, require players to use action, strategy, creativity, and social interaction, often with a competitive element [3]–[5], [27], [31]. Based on such findings, only students who played the listed games were considered as final participants.

The second part of the instrument includes the 30 five-point Likert-type scale questionnaire adapted from the FL classroom speaking confidence survey questionnaire [37], confidence in speaking English version 3 [38], and confidence questionnaire [39]. The statements from the surveys were carefully revised to meet the purposes of this study. The questionnaire was categorized based on the perceived effects of playing online video games on confidence of speaking in English or the dependent variables such as helpfulness in speaking skill development (HSSD), development of communication skills in English (DCSE), promoting active participation in class (PAPC), promoting active participation in pair and group activities (PAPPGA), reduced anxiety in using English (RAUE), and WTC in English (WCE). The final

survey items were crosschecked by two experts in the field of English language teaching (ELT) and education technology to ensure the reliability of the survey. It should be noted that the survey included an informed consent form that participants had to agree to before proceeding with the survey.

The main survey utilized for this study went through a pilot testing to ensure the reliability of the main instrument for data collection [40]. Then, Cronbach's alpha [41] was performed using SPSS 28, which exhibited a high level of reliability ($\alpha=0.903$) [41], [42]. After which, the survey was disseminated through faculty members in April and May 2023, and was posted through their e-portals (i.e., Messenger and Google Classroom). For accessibility, user-friendliness, and efficient collection of data from respondents, the survey was administered through Google Form [43]. Particularly, snowball sampling, as recommended by Freeman [44], was utilized to expand the sample gradually through referrals from initial participants.

3.3. Data analysis

This exploratory study employs a quantitative research design [45] to systematically analyze how learner variables affect the perceived influence of online video games on the overall confidence of Filipino college students in speaking English. To answer the research questions, descriptive statistics were used to present the profile of the respondents such as gender, time spent playing online, NOGP, and SRSP. Specifically, t-tests and analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS 28 [46] were used to analyze the differences between the respondents' variables and their confidence, which is defined as the perceived effect of playing online video games on the respondents' ability to speak English as measured by the dependent variables (i.e., HSSD, DCSE, PAPC, PAPPGA, RAUE, and WCE).

4. RESULTS

4.1. Respondents' profile

Table 1 shows the profile of the 148 out of 165 respondents who completed the survey. The other 17 respondents were not considered in the final analysis since they had not played any of the video games listed in the survey. Majority of respondents are female, 109 (73.6%) out of 148. In terms of TSOG, 63 respondents (42.6%) played less than one hour compared to 20 (13.5%) who played more than 5 hours. In addition, 119 respondents (80.4%) played at least three online video games per week. Lastly, 81 respondents (54.7%) self-rated their speaking proficiency in English as advanced.

4.2. Descriptive statistics of speaking confidence survey

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the categories from the survey. The results of the analysis of learners' perceived effects of playing online video games on their confidence in speaking English reveal a positive influence on HSSD with the highest mean of 3.769 (s.d.=0.622), followed by WCE with 3.667 mean (s.d.=0.668), while RAUE has the lowest mean of 3.281 (s.d.=0.705).

Table 1. Profile of the respondents

Learner variables		n (%)
Gender profile	Male	39 (26.4)
	Female	109 (73.6)
TSOG	0-1 hour	63 (42.6)
	1-3 hours	48 (32.4)
	3-5 hours	17 (11.5)
	More than 5 hours	20 (13.5)
NOGP	0-3 games	119 (80.4)
	4-6 games	17 (11.5)
	More than 6 games	12 (8.1)
SRSP	Advanced	81 (54.7)
	Intermediate	55 (37.2)
	Beginner	12 (8.1)

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of survey categories

Categories	m	s.d.
HSSD	3.769	0.622
DCSE	3.498	0.668
PAPC	3.366	0.649
PAPPGA	3.439	0.628
RAUE	3.281	0.705
WCE	3.667	0.644

Note: Decimal numbers rounded off to three decimal points

4.3. Video game categorization and learner experience in highly interactive and low interactive video games

The games were categorized into highly interactive (HI) and low interactive (LI). Categorizing the games based on specific criteria allowed for a structured comparison of their impact on speaking confidence, enhancing the analytical depth of this study. Table 3 presents the criteria considered in categorizing the games.

The games listed under HI (i.e., Call of Duty Mobile, CS: GO, Dota 2, Mobile Legends, LoL, Valorant, and Wild Rift) all fit the criteria for intense player interaction and strategic gameplay, which typically involve real-time battles against other players and demand quick reflexes and strategic thinking for success. They also belong to genres like MOBA, action RPG, MMORPG, or tactical shooters, which emphasize fast-paced competition and communication between players through voice chat. Conversely, the LI games like COC, Genshin Impact, Minecraft, and Roblox focus on less intense, sometimes turn-based, gameplay that allows for a more leisurely experience. These LI games involve simple building, exploration, and first-person shooting or casual mechanics, with less emphasis on immediate competitive skill or real-time player interactions.

Table 3. Categorization of video games

Feature	HI	LI
Player interaction	Intense	Less intense
Gameplay style	Facet-paced, competitive	Leisurely
Required skills	Strategic thinking, quick reflexes	Less immediate skill or strategy
Competitive gameplay	Real-time battles or matches	Often absent
Player communication	Text and voice chat features	May not be prioritized or has text chat feature only
Genres	MOBA, action RPG, MMORPG, tactical shooting	Building, exploration, first-person shooter, casual gaming

4.4. Results of analysis on learner experience in playing HI and LI video games

Table 4 presents the results of an independent t-test on the HI video games that respondents played based on the survey. The findings revealed a statistically significant difference on RAUE ($t=0.848$, $p=0.039$). This finding suggests that respondents who reported playing HI games had a slightly higher mean score ($m=3.271$, $s.d.=0.824$) than those who did not ($m=3.135$, $s.d.=0.660$). However, it is important to note that while HI games have a positive effect on RAUE among ESL learners who play them, those who do not play these games may have other strategies to manage their anxiety [30].

Table 4. Results of independent t-test by learner experience in playing HI video games

Categories	Response	m	s.d.	df	F	t	Sig.
HSSD	Yes	3.749	0.632	94	0.063	0.27	0.802
	No	3.712	0.681				
DCSE	Yes	3.470	0.710	94	0.010	0.714	0.920
	No	3.365	0.696				
PAPC	Yes	3.364	0.681	94	2.522	1.327	0.116
	No	3.184	0.585				
PAPPGA	Yes	3.525	0.656	94	0.232	1.711	0.631
	No	3.297	0.602				
RAUE	Yes	3.271	0.824	94	4.403	0.848	*0.039
	No	3.135	0.660				
WCE	Yes	3.718	0.697	94	0.302	1.073	0.584
	No	3.568	0.613				

Note: Decimal numbers rounded off to three decimal points, * $p<0.05$

On the other hand, Table 5 shows the results of the independent samples t-test for LI online video games. It is noted that there were no statistically significant differences between students who played the games and those who did not in terms of the surveyed categories, including HSSD, DCSE, PAPC, PAPPGA, RAUE, and WCE. Although not statistically significant, DCSE ($t=-1.339$, $p=0.054$) indicates that the use of LI video games may not directly impact or enhance students' confidence in speaking English.

4.5. Effect of gender on speaking confidence

Table 6 illustrates the results of an independent t-test analysis examining the speaking confidence by gender in the categories surveyed. Despite no statistically significant findings, WCE borders on statistical significance ($p=0.055$). These may indicate the importance of recognizing individual's ability and effort rather than relying solely on gender stereotypes when addressing speaking confidence in educational settings or other contexts [47].

Table 5. Results of independent t-test by learner experience in playing LI video games

Categories	Responses	m	s.d.	df	F	t	Sig.
HSSD	Yes	3.740	0.566	84	0.302	-1.719	0.584
	No	3.967	0.523				
DCSE	Yes	3.492	0.682	84	3.82	-1.339	0.054
	No	3.690	0.447				
PAPC	Yes	3.372	0.629	84	0.033	-1.449	0.857
	No	3.587	0.614				
PAPPGA	Yes	3.456	0.707	84	2.015	-0.618	0.159
	No	3.553	0.531				
RAUE	Yes	3.318	0.732	84	0.108	-0.715	0.743
	No	3.440	0.683				
WCE	Yes	3.699	0.579	84	0.217	-0.852	0.642
	No	3.813	0.519				

Note: Decimal numbers rounded off to three decimal points

Table 6. Results of independent t-test on speaking confidence by gender

Categories	Gender	m	s.d.	df	F	t	Sig.
HSSD	Male	3.872	0.563	146	0.636	1.203	0.427
	Female	3.732	0.639				
DCSE	Male	3.628	0.535	146	3.312	1.420	0.071
	Female	3.452	0.706				
PAPC	Male	3.462	0.543	146	3.475	1.082	0.064
	Female	3.332	0.674				
PAPPGA	Male	3.453	0.526	146	3.169	0.159	0.077
	Female	3.434	0.663				
RAUE	Male	3.405	0.620	146	2.282	1.283	0.133
	Female	3.237	0.731				
WCE	Male	3.709	0.542	146	3.750	0.482	0.055
	Female	3.651	0.678				

Note: Decimal numbers rounded off to three decimal points

4.6. Effect of time spent online gaming on speaking confidence

Table 7 presents the one-way ANOVA results of the effect of TSOG on various categories related to speaking confidence. Notably, there is a statistically significant effect of TOSG on DCSE at $p < 0.05$ ($F = 2.885$, $p = 0.038$). This finding may suggest that spending more time playing online games may increase DCSE, possibly due to the active interactions during gaming [30], [31].

Table 7. Results of one-way ANOVA on speaking confidence by TSOG

Categories	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
HSSD	2.663	3	0.888	2.361	0.074
DCSE	3.717	3	1.239	2.885	*0.038
PAPC	2.094	3	0.698	1.713	0.167
PAPPGA	1.029	3	0.343	0.867	0.460
RAUE	2.349	3	0.783	1.593	0.194
WCE	0.725	3	0.242	0.578	0.630

Note: Decimal numbers rounded off to three decimal point, * $p < 0.05$

4.7. Effect of number of games played on speaking confidence

The results of one-way ANOVA analysis in Table 8 show the impact of the NOGP by respondents on various categories related to speaking confidence. The analysis revealed that a higher NOGP was associated with a statistically significant increase in WCE ($F = 4.19$, $p = 0.017$). Such findings may suggest that playing a greater number of games may affect individuals' confidence and motivation to communicate in English, which may be due to their engagement while playing games [25], [31].

Table 8. Results of one-way ANOVA on speaking confidence by the NOGP

Categories	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
HSSD	1.215	2	0.608	1.585	0.209
DCSE	0.720	2	0.360	0.805	0.449
PAPC	0.855	2	0.427	1.034	0.358
PAPPGA	0.246	2	0.123	0.309	0.735
RAUE	0.898	2	0.449	0.902	0.408
WCE	3.326	2	1.663	4.190	*0.017

Note: Decimal numbers rounded off to three decimal points, * $p < 0.05$

4.8. Effects of self-rated speaking proficiency on speaking confidence

Table 9 illustrates how SRSP levels (i.e., beginner, intermediate, and advanced) affect categories that constitute speaking confidence. Firstly, speaking proficiency significantly impacted DCSE ($F=5.554$, $p=0.005$). Additionally, a significant effect of speaking proficiency on PAPC was found ($F=3.105$, $p=0.048$). Another noteworthy finding was the significant effect of speaking proficiency on RAUE ($F=6.638$, $p=0.002$). However, the statistically significant results, which primarily reflect respondents' perceptions of the impact of games on their English-speaking skills, suggest that lower proficient learners may perceive less benefit from video games, while higher proficient learners feel more confident in utilizing video games for language use. Such association indicates the need for appropriate interventions to address learners' differentiated perceptions according to different proficiency levels.

Table 9. Results of one-way ANOVA on speaking confidence by SRSP

Categories	Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
HSSD	2.027	2	1.014	2.683	0.072
DCSE	4.665	2	2.332	5.554	*0.005
PAPC	2.495	2	1.248	3.105	*0.048
PAPPGA	2.006	2	1.003	2.597	0.078
RAUE	6.132	2	3.066	6.638	*0.002
WCE	1.717	2	0.858	2.104	0.126

Note: Decimal numbers rounded off to three decimal points, * $p<0.05$

5. DISCUSSION

This exploratory study reveals insightful findings on the potential influence of online video gaming on Filipino college students' confidence in speaking English. First, the results of independent t-tests by respondents' experiences in playing HI video games revealed a statistically significant difference in RAUE. This finding corroborates with previous studies [4], [31], which supported that online multiplayer video games increased confidence and reduced anxiety regarding English language use of ESL learners. The significant role of HI games in reducing anxiety highlights the unique potential of interactive and competitive game environments, where students can use English in a low-pressure context. However, LI video games, revealed no statistically significant differences across dependent variables. Hence, these findings suggest that HI games can be beneficial for students in increasing students' confidence in speaking in English as such games were perceived to reduce their anxiety in using the language [22].

No gender difference was found in speaking confidence. Although according to previous several studies [5], [27], males who played COTS, MMORPGS, adventure games, and collaborative online games improved their language skills of speaking, listening, reading, writing, feedback, grammar, and vocabulary. The lack of gender difference in speaking confidence suggests that the benefits of online gaming for language skills may apply broadly across genders [26], despite previous findings indicating that male players often experience greater gains in specific language skills. On the other hand, TSOG on DCSE and increased WCE due to a higher NOGP per week showed statistically significant results. These findings suggest that frequent and immersive gaming experiences can actively support increased confidence and use of English, and further improve other communication skills [24], [25], [30], [31]. However, teachers should keep in mind that unrestricted and excessive online video games could potentially hinder the affordances of online video games in developing students' confidence in speaking English and decrease motivation in language learning by neglecting the real-world situations [24], [32].

SRSP significantly impacted DCSE, PAPC, and RAUE. These findings suggest that proficiency serves as a foundational element that enhances the effectiveness of online games as a language practice tool for higher proficiency learners, who may engage more deeply in interactive language use within game contexts. According to previous studies [33], [34], echo that as speaking proficiency improves, learners feel more comfortable expressing themselves in English, which can lead to increased confidence in their speaking abilities. Hence, learners with lower English-speaking proficiency levels may perceive less benefits from online gaming, while learners with higher proficiency levels may utilize games better for language use. With such results, this study highlights the need for game-based interventions that can be beneficial across varying proficiency levels to ensure all learners gain confidence in their speaking abilities.

This exploratory study, based on the perceptions of selected Filipino college students, advances their views on the potential influence of online video games on their overall confidence in speaking English—an area that remains underexplored in the Philippine context. Therefore, to fully realize such findings, it is suggested that language teachers integrate online interactive video games into their language classrooms and investigate the relationship between learner variables and their effect on learners' confidence in speaking English. It is also important to consider learners' gaming habits and preferences in relation to their overall

confidence in speaking English. To further fill the gap in the scarcity of research on this phenomenon in the Philippine context and in language teaching in general, empirical studies should investigate other factors and examine the application of online video games as a tool to address concerns on speaking confidence.

6. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study emphasize the potential of online video games as supplemental tools for improving learners' overall confidence in speaking English (e.g., communication skills, active class participation, reduced anxiety, and WTE). However, ELT practitioners should consider the potential drawbacks of excessive gaming such as decreased academic task completion, reduced cognitive abilities due to sleep disturbances, lack of motivation in language learning, and negligence of real-world responsibilities can lead to distractions rather than increase in language skills development. Accordingly, they should find a balanced approach, which promotes moderation and addresses potential distractions to maximize benefits of online video games. In doing so, HI online games can contribute to the effective design of language instruction, thereby facilitating language skill development.

While this study provides valuable insights into the benefits of online video games (e.g., MOBA, action RPG, MMORPG, strategy video games, and survival or tactical shooter games) or games primarily for entertainment in potentially improving learners' overall confidence in speaking English, several limitations and recommendations should be considered. First, the study examined students' perceptions drawn from utilizing a survey only. Future research could employ experimental studies and qualitative research, such as interviews and observations, to assess to what extent online video games can enhance students' participation and language development. Second, other variables such as game genre preferences and game mechanics should be considered in future studies to evaluate their impact on the effectiveness of online games in language learning. Third, instead of relying on SRSP, future research could use standardized proficiency tests such as IELTS, TOEFL, or TOEIC for more objective measures. Finally, this study was exploratory and focused only on the perceived influence of online video games on the English-speaking confidence of a selected group of Filipino college students. Future studies should aim to survey a larger and more diverse sample to increase the generalizability of the findings.

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C : Conceptualization

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O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

INFORMED CONSENT

An informed consent was not necessary for this research.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

An ethics board review approval does not apply to this research.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The instrument utilized for this study is openly available at <https://shorturl.at/wRrIt>.

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